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DEGLI STUDI
DI PADOVA

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Dipartimento di Fisica e Astronomia
Dipartimento di Ingegneria Industriale

Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare
Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro

**ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI FISICA
NUCLEARE**
Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro

MASTER THESIS

in

“Surface Treatments for Industrial Applications”

**DEVELOPMENT OF MAGNETRON SPUTTERING
Nb₃Sn TARGETS VIA LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION**

Supervisor: C. Pira

Student: Matteo Zanierato
N. Matr.: 2026448

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Dedicata a tutta la mia famiglia.

Abstract

The performance of the Nb bulk cavities has now reached the theoretical limits imposed by the material. It is necessary to look at other superconducting materials, among which the most promising is Nb₃Sn.

The deposition of Nb₃Sn on copper cavities is interesting for the higher thermal conductivity of copper compared to common Nb substrates. The better heat exchange would allow the use of cryocoolers reducing cryogenic costs and the risk of thermal quench [1]. Magnetron sputtering technology allows the deposition of Nb₃Sn on substrates different than Nb, however the coating of substrates with complex geometry (such as elliptical cavities) may require target with non-planar shape, difficult to realize with classic powder sintering techniques.

In this work, the possibility of using the Liquid Tin Diffusion (LTD) technique to produce sputtering targets is explored. The LTD technique is a wire fabrication technology, already developed in the past at LNL for SRF applications [2], that allows the deposition of very thick and uniform coating on Nb substrates even with complex geometry [3]. Improvements in LTD process, proof of concept of a single use LTD target production, and characterization of the Nb₃Sn film coated by DC magnetron sputtering with these innovative targets are reported in this thesis work.

INTRODUCTION

Superconducting radiofrequency (SRF) accelerating cavities are the heart of modern particle accelerators. Superconductors are characterized by the critical temperature (T_c) below which they exhibit zero electrical resistance. In radiofrequency there are also losses due to surface resistance. The Nb_3Sn has an operating temperature of 18 K twice that of Nb (9 K) that allows to operate at 4.2 K instead of actual 2 K of Nb bulk cavities, reducing the cryogenic costs of more than 50 % [4,5]. Moreover, a superheating field (H_{sh}) of 425 mT pushes the accelerating field limit up to 100 MV / m (for Nb is less than 50 MV / m).

Another important aspect of Nb_3Sn is a high value of critical field of 24 T. This feature makes the material suitable for all applications where a high magnetic field is required, such as cavities for finding dark matter particles as Axions.

The state of the art of Nb_3Sn cavities on Nb bulk (Nb_3Sn / Nb) is represented by the synthesis using the Vapor Tin Diffusion (VTD) technique. In this process, tin is evaporated and by condensation-diffusion a thin film of few μm is obtained, but it is insufficient to completely shield the surface currents [5]. In the practical use of a Nb_3Sn / Nb cavity at the interface there is heating due to the Joule effect which involves the transition from superconductor to normal conductor, establishing the current limit of use of 20 MV / m.

Nb_3Sn deposition on copper cavities is interesting for the higher thermal conductivity of copper compared to common Nb substrates. The Magnetron sputtering technology allows the deposition of Nb_3Sn substrates with complex geometry may require non-conventional targets, difficult to achieve with classic powder sintering techniques.

Various international groups are working on the production of Nb_3Sn / Cu films. Currently only small planar samples and no cavities of this type have been produced yet.

The Liquid Tin Diffusion (LTD) technique, previously developed at LNL for superconductivity applications in RF [2], has recently been rediscovered for the production of PVD targets. This methodology currently allows the production of thick films sufficient for a single deposition via sputtering [3]. Diffusion in the LTD occurs in a liquid state by dipping the Nb in the molten tin.

The Direct Current Magnetron Sputtering (DCMS) technique carried out with Nb_3Sn targets would provide the advantage of having a cathode with

correct stoichiometry and phase at the start, avoiding more complex deposition geometries with the use of multiple targets.

I developed a process to make thick films of Nb_3Sn on Niobium substrates with complex geometry using the LTD technique during both my master's thesis and the first-level short specialization degree at INFN. The nucleation process has been optimised and studied in detail in its various steps. In the following work, a simple solid state chemistry model will be presented for the interpretation of the formation of percolative paths along the film.

In order to test the goodness of the process obtained $\text{Nb}_3\text{Sn}/\text{Nb}$ cavities were produced.

DCMS deposition with planar targets obtained via LTD allows to validate this synthesis methodology as a good route for the fabrication of subsequent cylindrical cathodes.

Summary

Abstract.....	II
INTRODUCTION	II
THEORETICAL SECTION	
1 CHAPTER 1.....	1
1.1 FUNDAMENTALS OF SUPERCONDUCTIVITY	2
1.2 SUPERCONDUCTING RADIOFREQUENCY CAVITIES	4
2 CHAPTER 2.....	7
2.1 Nb ₃ Sn A15 STRUCTURE.....	10
2.2 VAPOUR TIN DIFFUSION (VTD)	11
2.3 BRONZE PROCESS (SOLID STATE DIFFUSION).....	12
2.4 LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION (LTD)	13
2.5 SPUTTERING.....	14
3 CHAPTER 3	15
3.1 SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE (SEM)	16
3.2 X-RAY DIFFRACTOMETER (XRD).....	16
3.3 PROFILOMETER.....	16
3.4 X-RAY PHOTOELECTRON SPECTROSCOPY (XPS)	17
3.5 RF CHARACTERISATION	17
3.6 RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY	18
3.7 T _c MEASUREMENT.....	18
3.8 A.C. MULTI-HARMONIC MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY CHARACTERIZATION	19

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION	
4 CHAPTER 4	21
4.1 LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION (LTD) SYSTEM	22
4.2 Nb ₃ Sn SPUTTERING SYSTEM.....	24
5 CHAPTER 5	25
5.1 LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION PROCESSES.....	26
5.1.2 NUCLEATION AND COATING.....	26
5.1.3 DIPPING	34
5.1.4 ANNEALING	35
5.1.5 ACCELERATING RESONANT CAVITIES.....	41
5.1.6 CAVITIES FOR AXIONS.....	43
5.1.7 Nb ₃ Sn PLANAR TARGET.....	46
5.2 Nb ₃ Sn DC MAGNETRON SPUTTERING	48
6 CHAPTER 6	51
6.1 CONCLUSIONS	52
6.2 FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS	53
6.3 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	53

REFERENCES

THEORETICAL SECTION

In this section, the theoretical fundamentals behind superconductivity and diffusion processes will be reported.

CHAPTER 1

FUNDAMENTALS

This chapter will briefly outline the basics of superconductivity of interest to
Nb₃Sn.

1.1 FUNDAMENTALS OF SUPERCONDUCTIVITY

Superconductivity is the property of some materials to exhibit zero resistance when a direct current (DC) is applied. The fundamental properties of a superconducting state (SC) are the transition from a finite resistivity (ρ_n) in the normal state above a specific critical temperature (T_c) characteristic of the material, to $\rho=0$ below this T_c . The T_c becomes a key parameter for understanding the physics of the superconductor. In the case of the Nb_3Sn , the critical temperature gives information about the correct stoichiometry of the material and vice versa.

A superconductor has perfect diamagnetism. There is a change in magnetic susceptibility from a small and positive value, characteristic of paramagnetism, to a value of $\chi=-1$ below T_c . This can be deduced from the Meissner-Ochsenfeld effect : the complete expulsion of the magnetic field from the interior of the superconductor.

1.1.1 MAGNETISM

The SC material placed at a $T < T_c$ ejects the magnetic field, due to the shielding superficial currents on the surface of the material which induce a magnetic field equal and opposite to that in which the material is immersed. This is only true if the applied field does not exceed the value of the material's own critical field H_c . The characteristic critical field is a function of temperature with a parabolic trend of the type:

$$H_c(T) = H_c(0) \cdot [1 - (T/T_c)^2] \quad \text{eq.(1-1)}$$

With $H_{c(0)}$ critical field is calculated at 0 K. This parabolic trend is valid for all type I superconductors [6,7].

In the diagram of type II superconductive materials (**Fig. 1-1**), which includes Nb_3Sn , there is also a mixed conduction zone characterised by the presence of vortices whose centre is a normal conductor. The flux in the mixed state enters in a quantized manner. A fluxon is defined as the amount of flux energy:

$$\phi_0 = \frac{hc}{2e} \quad \text{eq(1-2)}$$

The greater the external magnetic field, the greater the vortex density. When H_{c2} is exceeded, the material permeated by the vortices returns to normal conductor state (**Fig. 1-1**).

Fig. 1-1 : Meissner state for a type II SC material and its magnetization curve [6].

1.1.2 TWO FLUID MODEL

The first to introduce this model were Gorter and Casimir [6] to explain zero resistance and diamagnetism. The charge carriers can be distinguished into two fluids, one superconducting (SC) and one normal-conducting (NC). By defining n as the density of the carriers, the relationships for the densities of the corresponding currents are obtained:

$$J_s = -n_s e v_s \quad \Rightarrow \quad n = n_s + n_n \quad \text{so} \quad J = J_s + J_n \quad \text{eq.(1-3)}$$

Where the subscripts indicate the SC and NC species. The total current therefore has both contributions. It follows from London's first equation that the superconductive fluid is not affected by collisions, whereas the normal-conductive fluid is affected by collisions. The relationship between the density of superconducting carriers (n_s) and temperature is defined as :

$$n_s = n_0 \left(1 - \left(\frac{T}{T_c} \right)^4 \right) \quad \text{eq.(1-4)}$$

By lowering the temperature relative to T_c , the number of superconductive carriers increases significantly. From this expression it is clear why new materials with higher T_c than niobium are to be used. Indeed, at a given temperature the number of carriers is higher in a material with a high T_c . Basically, a material like Nb_3Sn has better properties than Nb. The density trend is such that n_s decreases with increasing temperature until it annihilates at T_c , while n_n has the opposite trend as shown in **Fig. 1-2 [8]**.

Fig. 1-2 : Graph of the change in density of superconducting (n_s) and normal conducting (n_n) charge carriers as a function of temperature.

The current cannot exist only on the surface, but must penetrate a certain thickness depending on the type of material. The more electrons per unit volume, the shorter the penetration length defined as λ_L . Therefore, London's penetration length is a damping constant of the field. This length expresses the depth of the zone where the persistent currents generated on the surface of the material are located and can be expressed as :

$$\lambda_L^2 = \varepsilon_0 \frac{mc^2}{n_s e^2} \quad \text{eq.(1-5)}$$

Where m is the mass of the electron, c the speed of light, n_s the superconducting electron density, e is the electron charge.

Considering now time-varying fields, then switching to the RF regime, the total current can still be expressed as before.

$$J = (\sigma_1 - i\sigma_2)E = \sigma_{\text{eff}}E \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{\sigma_1}{\sigma_n} = \frac{n_n}{n} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_n} = \left(\frac{n_n}{n}\right)\omega\tau + \left(\frac{n_s}{n}\right)\frac{1}{\omega\tau} \quad \text{eq.(1-6)}$$

From the above equations it can be seen that at zero frequency the conductivity is infinite, whereas when the frequency deviates from zero the resulting dissipation is non-zero.

From the laws just described, it can be understood that a superconducting material has zero resistance only in DC, but in RF there is dissipation, although considerably less than in a material in its normal state.

A comprehensive explanation of surface resistance from temperature and frequency is given by BCS theory, which describes the phenomenon from a microscopic point of view [9].

1.2 SUPERCONDUCTING RADIOFREQUENCY CAVITIES

A resonant cavity is a region of space enclosed by a surface of conductive material that can store a certain amount of energy within it. Similarly to a low-frequency resonant circuit, the energy is in the form of stationary oscillating electromagnetic waves [7].

1.2.1 SKIN EFFECT

Electrons are distributed over the surface of a conductor in the normal state. Classically, Ohm's law applies and in the case of time-varying fields, the current density lags behind this field due to the inertia of the electrons. Hence J and E are out of phase-time. Considering a semi-infinite plane of reference, the electromagnetic field will penetrate for a given thickness (δ skin depth of the field).

We can imagine that the electromagnetic field, penetrating inside the metal, induces a current density. The energy carried by the radiation is transferred to the electrons, which in turn transfer it to the underlying material lattice.

The fields only penetrate the conductor for a certain thickness comparable to the length δ , known as the penetration length of the skin effect.

Assuming a pulsation of the wave ω such that $\omega\tau \ll 1$, where τ is the average time that elapses between two successive collisions of a conduction electron, we obtain that:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\mu_0 \mu \omega \sigma}} \quad \text{eq.(1-7)}$$

where ω is the pulse of the wave and σ is the conductivity of the metal.

The impedance has an imaginary part because the surface field is not in phase with the total current in the conductor due to the rate of change of the magnetic flux in the conductor. The real part R_s gives the surface resistance in RF, and the imaginary part X_s represents the reactance. The surface resistance in RF can therefore be expressed as:

$$R_s = X_s = \frac{1}{\sigma\delta} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0\mu\omega}{2\sigma}} \quad \text{eq.(1-8)}$$

It is derived from the skin effect that the surface resistance of a conducting material increases as $\omega^{1/2}$. This behaviour is only observed at low frequencies, whereas as the frequency increases, the conductivity σ becomes saturated, showing a behaviour called anomalous skin effect.

At low temperature $\sigma(T)$ increases and δ decreases. This parameter can become lower than the mean free path of the electrons, because only electrons travelling almost parallel to the surface participate in conduction.

The anomalous skin effect consists of a higher surface resistance at low temperature than would be expected. This undermines the use of materials such as copper, and more generally normal-conducting materials, at cryogenic temperatures. The cost, in terms of power, for the helium bath is much higher than the power and efficiency obtained from the cavity.

1.2.2 ENERGY STORAGE

The energy stored in the resonator is transferred to the particles when they pass through the cavity in the same direction as the electric field. The accelerating function of a cavity is summarised by the parameter E_{acc} , called the accelerating field. This is the field responsible for the gain of potential energy per unit charge V_{acc} that a particle acquires when crossing the longitudinal axis of the cavity of length L . The accelerating voltage can be defined as:

$$V_c = E_0 \left| \int_0^d e^{i\frac{\omega_0 z}{c}} dz \right| = dE_0 T \quad \text{eq.(1-9)}$$

Where V_c is the acceleration voltage, E_0 is the electric field injected by the coupler, T is the travel time of the long cavity d , and T must be half the RF period.

In a real cavity, consisting of walls of conductive material with finite surface resistance, the electromagnetic field induces surface currents in the area of penetration. These currents dissipate energy by the Joule effect. The dissipation is proportional to the surface resistance of the material, which on the walls results in a progressive decrease of the total energy stored: the slower the decay, the better the behaviour of the cavity.

To express the quality of the device quantitatively, as efficiency in storing energy, the Q factor is used. For a generic resonant element, excited in a particular normal mode, we define a parameter Q called the merit factor:

$$Q = 2\pi f \frac{U}{P_d} \quad \text{eq.(1-10)}$$

Where f is the normal mode resonance frequency, U is the total energy stored in the cavity and P_d is the total power dissipated at the walls.

The power dissipation can be expressed:

$$P_d = \frac{1}{2} R_s \int_S |H|^2 ds \quad \text{eq.(1-11)}$$

Where integration takes place by considering the surface resistance of the internal cavity constant (R_s) [6, 8].

Generally, the actual devices for the application are used at $T < 1$ K; however, even at lower temperatures there remains a residual R_{res} term.

Cooper pairs move without friction, so should not create dissipation but this is only true in DC and not in RF as shown in **Fig. 1-3**.

In the surface layer of the material there will be an electric field that accelerates and decelerates the normal carriers, which generates dissipation proportional to the square of the RF frequency.

As a first approximation, the surface resistance can be expressed as the sum of two terms: the first R_{BCS} described by the BCS theory and dependent on temperature, and a second term R_{res} which is constant as the temperature varies and depends on innumerable factors.

The total surface resistance can therefore be expressed as:

$$R_s(T) = R_{BCS}(T) + R_{res} \quad \text{eq.(1-12)}$$

Fig. 1-3 : Change in resistance of a superconductor in the radio frequency regime.

1.2.3 Q_0 LIMITATIONS IN ACCELERATING CAVITIES

The experimental Q VS E_{acc} curve of a superconducting cavity is not flat, as would be expected from BCS theory, but shows different characteristics as the accelerating field increases. Some of the contributions are shown in **Fig. 1-4** and the influence on the overall quality factor is displayed graphically.

Q-slope of the mean field: it is generally attributed to a combination due to surface heating and non-linear BCS resistance. Annealing generally reduces this problem.

Q-drop in the higher field region: it can be explained by the fact that the superconductivity ceases due to a thermal instability triggered by local heating about to defect or a phase transition in the local critical magnetic field RF [10].

Multipacting: is a resonant process in which many electrons make multiple impacts with the cavity walls. This phenomenon absorbs RF power, which makes it impossible to increase the field in the cavity by increasing the delivered power. In order to avoid this phenomenon, the accelerating cavities have an appropriate profile to bring the electrons to the equatorial zone where the accelerating field is zero. The geometrical shape of the tesla cavities is therefore essential to annihilate the multipacting phenomenon.

Fig. 1-4 : Main limiting factors in superconducting cavities [7].

Field emission: when the acceleration gradient is 10 to 20 MV / m, field emission can occur and in this case the Q_0 of a cavity begins to fall exponentially. In the presence of a high electric field, RF power is lost by electrons flowing out of the cavity wall at localised points. The emitted electrons are accelerated by the electromagnetic fields and, on impact, heat the cavity wall and produce X-rays.

Thermal quench: transition to normal-conductor due to overheating of the cavity

Vortices' creep: this dissipation mechanism is predominant in cavities where a high magnetic field is used and not an accelerating field. Axion cavities, presented in the next section, are subject to this dissipation mechanism; however, accelerating cavities with a peak magnetic field may also present similar problems. A dissipation mechanism may exist if the electric or magnetic field is such that it causes the vortices in Type II SCs to reorient or flow.

1.2.4 CAVITIES FOR AXIONS

In the 1970 R.D. Peccei, H. Quinn, S. Weinberg and F. Wilczek [11], hypothesised the existence of a new fundamental particle called Axion. The introduction of this species is necessary to explain why electric charges are homogeneously distributed within a neutron and do not form an electric dipole. It is predicted that axions can have masses between $(10\text{-}10^3)$ μeV [12].

The cavities of interest in this thesis project have been developed within the QUAX (QUAerere AXion) experiment at the INFN National Laboratories of Legnaro. Basically, the experiment aims to verify the existence of axions with a mass between 20 and 200 μeV . The cavities have a central body, which is the pillbox where the superconductive material of interest is synthesised.

The operation is conceptually different from accelerating cavities, since the external field created by a super-magnet must necessarily penetrate the cavity. Some cavity prototypes have selected areas to allow penetration of the external B-field. Given this consideration, it follows that only type II superconducting materials such as NbTi and Nb₃Sn have the necessary characteristics not to transition to the normal-conductive state and limit the Q factor.

1.2.5 Q-SLOPE IN AXION CAVITIES

The final experiment requires the development of resonators for high frequencies > 10 GHz. By definition, the characteristic size of such a structure is inverse to frequency; however, it is desired to use as much volume as available to maximise the energy signal. One solution is to use superconducting films to optimise the Q factor.

In real measurements for axion research, a limitation of the cavity is due to vortex creep; the thickness of the film should not exceed the characteristic spacing of the vortices to minimise the number of those parallel to the surface. An important factor in this respect is the uniformity of the external magnetic field applied to the resonant cavity, the greater the uniformity, the less the flow and reorientation of the vortices. A high B_{C2} Nb₃Sn coating would help the material not to transition and increase performance as shown in Fig. 1-5.

Fig. 1-5 : Quality factor Q_0 versus external magnetic field B for the hybrid NbTi /copper cavity, compared to the bulk copper cavity (blue horizontal line). ZFC points are measured by cooling the cavity before increasing the field. The second image shows the quality factor trends for different coating types and bulk cavities from 14.46 GHz TM_{110} [13].

CHAPTER 2

Nb₃Sn: CHARACTERISTICS AND METHODS OF SYNTHESIS

In this chapter, the main characteristics of Nb₃Sn are introduced, followed by the possible synthesis methods currently used to produce it on Nb and Cu substrates.

2.1 Nb₃Sn A15 STRUCTURE

Nb₃Sn is an electronic compound with a structure defined as A15 (**Fig. 2-1**). These binary intermetallic compounds have the particularity of exhibiting behaviour like covalent-ionic solids. In concentrations other than the A15 phase, metal alloys are usually formed. This class of compounds exhibit superconductivity due to the long-range ordering of superconducting elements. The critical parameters are raised because the lattice pitch between the A atoms in the structure is smaller than in the pure A material. Generally, electron-phonon interactions increase causing the increase in performance [4].

Fig. 2-1 : Representation of the A15-type unit cell for Nb₃Sn. The chains of "A" atoms bisect the faces of the bcc lattice [4].

The structure is body centred cubic (bcc) and belongs to the $O_h^3-P_m3_n$ space group. Nb has a distance between first neighbouring atoms of 0.286 nm, whereas in the Nb₃Sn chains each atom is 0.265 nm away from its neighbour [14].

The maximum critical temperature measured for Nb₃Sn is 18.3 K, and it is the only A15 material that has given promising results when applied to the construction of a real SRF cavity [2]. It is considered as the alternative material to Niobium that could really allow the increase of the performance of accelerating cavities [1, 2].

From the phase diagram in **Fig. 2-2** (left), it can be seen that phase A15 is formed from a peritectic at 2130°C which includes about 18% Sn. Below 1800°C the homogeneity range extends to 25.1%, thus including the stoichiometric composition A₃B. Phase A15 is stable up to room temperature, but its range gradually narrows to 22-25% from 1300 to 600°C.

At Sn concentrations of more than 24.5% at a temperature of about 43 K, a martensitic transition occurs in the material, with the crystal structure changing from cubic to tetragonal.

Plotting the critical temperature against the Nb/Sn ratio, it can be observed that if the Nb percentage deviates from the ideal stoichiometry of 75%, the performance of the superconductor decreases significantly **Fig. 2-2** (right). The effect is due to the dual mechanism of enrichment and depletion of one metal relative to the other. Within the stability range of phase A15 between 18% and 25% Sn, the T_c of Nb₃Sn goes from about 18.3 K to 6 K [4].

VAPOUR TIN DIFFUSION (VTD)

Fig. 2-2 : Phase diagram of the Nb-Sn system. In the box the phase diagram at low temperature, with the stability interval for the tetragonal structure [2, 4] (left). Critical temperature as a function of composition, for Nb₃Sn [4] (right).

The formation of the A15 phase can be accompanied by the parasitic phenomenon of the generation of spurious phases, such as amorphous Nb₃Sn ($T_c = 3.1$ K) and Sn-rich phases such as Nb₆Sn₅ ($T_c = 2.6$ K) and NbSn₂ ($T_c = 2.1$ K). Usually, these formations are located in grain boundaries [4]. In certain cases, contamination by residual Sn ($T_c = 3.7$ K) can occur. These problems are found in both accelerating and axion cavities, however in elliptical cavities the formation of Sn drops is greater.

2.2 VAPOUR TIN DIFFUSION (VTD)

This method is the state of the art for coating accelerator cavities with Nb₃Sn. This methodology has undergone various changes in order to optimise the process. The first process was carried out by Siemens and later improved by Wuppertal. Both tend to improve cavity performance. The disadvantage of these processes lies in reproducibility. Cornell was the first to regain and improve on Wuppertal's performance. Fermilab currently manages to obtain 5 and 9-cell cavities by modifying the positioning of the crucibles [5].

In the most general case, the diffusion system consists of a UHV ultra-high vacuum furnace with an inner lining chamber insulated from the one below containing the tin crucible which is then heated separately. The inner chamber is equipped externally with a further furnace for heating the zone, this is necessary for subsequent annealing.

The diagram of the coating apparatus and relative temperature using the Wuppertal method is shown in Fig. 2-3 . The coating procedure used is described below.

Degassing: backing of 24+ hours at 180°C, after 2 hours of crucible pre-heating.

Nucleation: A 5 hour nucleation stage at 500°C during which the SnCl₂ agent is introduced and decomposes on the substrate to form tin nucleation sites, promoting layer uniformity.

Ramp: A ramp is set for the coating temperatures, during which a gradient of > 100°C is maintained between the source and the chamber.

Coating: the constant temperature coating stage, during which the source is always kept at a higher temperature than the chamber.

Annealing step: In this stage the source heater is turned off allowing the source to cool to the temperature of the chamber where the sample is located. At the end of the annealing phase, the sample furnace is turned off and allowed to cool naturally for as long as necessary.

Fig. 2-3 : Diagram of a diffusion apparatus with the Wuppertal method (left) and description of the temperatures in the various steps (right) [5].

The Nb substrate is anodised prior to the diffusion process. Electrolytic anodising induces a 70 nm growth of the niobium oxide layer, which gives the sample a blue colour. This layer allows SnCl₂ to adsorb and chemically adsorb and then, via a redox reaction at the interface, deposit metallic Sn which will act as a nucleation centre.

The main problem with the process is an uneven film thickness. In areas with a thickness of less than 500 nm, currents are not fully shielded and interfere at the interface causing thermal quenching.

2.3 BRONZE PROCESS (SOLID STATE DIFFUSION)

The bronze process is the process by which multifilament cables are commercially produced for the manufacture of Nb₃Sn based magnets. In this type of process, solid phase diffusion is used: the niobium substrate is embedded in a bronze (Cu-Sn) matrix and heated to a temperature of approximately 700°C. At this temperature, due to solid-state diffusion of the tin from the bronze to the niobium, an Nb₃Sn film is formed at the interface between the wire and the matrix.

2.4 LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION (LTD)

LTD diffusion derives from the industrial technique known as hot dip galvanisation (if done with Zn), which are among the milestones in the industry for coating steel or cast iron surfaces. Dipping is also used for the manufacture of SC cables in Nb_3Sn ; from this application came the initial idea of applying the process to cavities.

This technique requires a low level of technological equipment leading to a modest economic impact. The main difference to the vapour diffusion system is the introduction of the sample or massive Nb cavity into the molten tin bath (99.99% purity) for limited periods of time (minimum 15 minutes). Molten tin allows faster nucleation directly on niobium without using the nucleating agent $SnCl_2$.

The instrumentation consists of a cylindrical high-vacuum reaction chamber containing an alumina crucible for the tin bath and a linear manipulator to move the samples from the top to the bottom and vice versa.

Generally, a procedure can be summarised in the following steps as shown in Fig. 2-4 [2, 3].

Degassing: backing of 24+ hours at variable temperature usually 200°C.

Thermalization: the specimen is held over the molten tin bath in order to achieve an adequate temperature to avoid thermal shock that would occur if the cold cavity were placed in the molten tin. This step minimises the possibility of thermal stress formation.

Dipping: the cavity in the molten pool and holding for a given period of time.

Annealing: in this step the procedures differ considerably. If a second furnace is present, the system does not need to be opened and annealing is carried out. In this case a further differentiation can be made according to whether the sample can still be subjected to Sn flow or not.

Fig. 2-4 : variation of temperatures as a function of time in an LTD process [3].

2.5 SPUTTERING

Sputtering is a deposition technology that falls under the heading of PVD (physical vapour deposition). It is an atomic deposition process in which material is vaporised from a solid source in the form of atoms or molecules and transported as vapour from the low-pressure environment to the substrate, where it condenses as shown in **Fig. 2-5** [1, 15].

Vapour deposition processes require ultra-high vacuum conditions in the specific case of superconducting films; this is essential to limit the presence of pollutants and to obtain an optimal free mean path for plasma formation.

The process requires the ignition of a plasma between a cathode consisting of the material to be evaporated and an anode (usually the substrate), which is electrically connected to the deposition chamber itself and grounded for safety reasons. The plasma in the sputtering process is generated by applying a sufficiently high DC voltage. It is necessary to cool the target in order to dissipate the energy released by the ions, which could damage it. The ions of the gas in which the discharge occurs collide with the cathode consisting of the material to be sputtered, causing the ejection of atoms or molecules. The energy of the ions is approximately 30 eV, while the atoms are ejected with an energy of 10 eV.

Improved performance can be achieved by increasing the number of ions produced by a single electron by increasing the length of the path it takes before colliding with the positive electrode of the system. One method of achieving this is to apply a confining magnetic field parallel to the cathode surface. A magnetron sputtering system has essentially the same configuration as described above, with the addition of an external magnetic field to increase the ionisation efficiency of the electrons.

The net effect of applying a magnetic field is to sputter at lower pressures or, similarly, to obtain higher currents (and thus higher deposition rates) at the same pressure compared to a diode system. On the other hand, this causes a strong heating of the target, which has to be cooled, also to avoid exceeding the Curie temperature, which would make the magnets ineffective [1, 3].

Nb₃Sn can be deposited directly with a target of the same material sintered from powders or with a co-deposition of Nb-Sn and subsequent annealing.

Fig. 2-5 : Description of a DCMS direct current magnetron sputtering process [1, 15].

CHAPTER 3

CHARACTERIZATION METHODS

The main characterisation techniques used are briefly listed below.

3.1 SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE (SEM)

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) is one of the most versatile tools available for the examination and morphological analysis of microstructure and for characterising chemical composition. Combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), it can perform fast, high-resolution elemental analysis (5 % error), so the composition can be understood and chemical mapping of the film along the diffusion direction can be achieved [3].

The various SEM techniques are differentiated on the basis of what you decide to detect:

Secondary electrons: the most common imaging mode is based on the detection of these electrons, which are located in the lowest portion of the emitted energy distribution. They allow 2D-3D visualisation of the sample morphology.

Backscattered electrons: backscattered electrons are electrons that bounce back elastically and therefore have the same energy as incident electrons. They allow the chemical component to be weighted more heavily than the morphology, highlighting variations in composition.

EDS (Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometry): electrons emitted from the filament (cathode) are accelerated to high energies and strike the sample target (anode). In the process, characteristic X-rays of the atoms in the irradiated area are emitted. By analysing their energies, the atoms can be identified and by counting the number of X-rays, the concentration of atoms in the area can be determined.

The samples are sheared or cut by electro-erosion, embedded in carbon filler and lapped. In this work, a CX-200 PLUS is used as SEM and a Bruker X-Lash Detector 410-M is used for EDS analysis.

3.2 X-RAY DIFFRACTOMETER (XRD)

Diffraction analysis allows information to be obtained on the type of crystal structure of the film. It is possible to obtain information on the presence of spurious phases that are not of interest. The instrument used is a Bragg diffractometer "X'Pert-Pro" from Philips. The instrumentation was calibrated with polycrystalline Si standards. Any Rietveld refinements and processing were done with High-Score Plus and MAUD software.

3.3 PROFILOMETER

A Veeco Dektat 8 profilometer was used to check the thickness of the deposited films. The instrument consists of a diamond tip which slides over the sample to be measured by pressing on it with a constant force. The roughness of the surface is reflected in a vertical movement of the tip and the cantilever in which it is fixed. The cantilever is connected to a capacitor, and the vertical movement of the tip results in a change in the capacitance, which the system converts into a profile displayed on the PC screen. The sample to be measured must be flat and hard enough not to be scratched by the tip. The non-deposited area is obtained by masking part of the substrate.

3.4 X-RAY PHOTOELECTRON SPECTROSCOPY (XPS)

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is a surface-sensitive quantitative spectroscopic technique based on the photoelectric effect that can identify the elements that exist within a material or are covering its surface, as well as their chemical state, and the overall electronic structure and density of the electronic states in the material.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out with a Perkin Elmer Φ 5600ci Multi Technique System in collaboration with Jonathan Cavazzani (IMPACT group) of the chemical department (DISC) of UNIPD .

The spectrometer was calibrated by assuming the binding energy (BE) of the Au 4f 7/2 line to be 84.0 eV with respect to the Fermi level. The spectra for qualitative and also high-resolution spectra for quantitative analysis (23,5 eV pass energy, 0.1 eV/step, 0.1 s/step) were collected with a standard Al K α source working at 200 W. The standard deviation in the BE values of the XPS line is 0.10 eV. The atomic percentage was evaluated using the PHI sensitivity factors after a Shirley-type background subtraction. The peak positions were corrected for the charging effects by considering the C 1s peak at 285.0 eV and evaluating the BE differences.

3.5 RF CHARACTERISATION

Resonant cavities are characterised by measuring the merit factor as the applied accelerating field changes, as the energy stored in the resonator changes. In this way, information is obtained on both the energy yield of the device and the maximum accelerating power towards a charged particle.

The cavity excited under resonant conditions contains stored energy in the form of stationary electromagnetic waves. These waves are the result of currents circulating on the surface of the material, within a thickness that depends on the penetration of the fields.

After cooling the cavity below its critical temperature, it is possible to proceed with radiofrequency measurement. The first step is to determine the resonance frequency by means of a frequency scan. The cavity is fed with an RF stimulus via a coupler antenna inside the resonator. A small (negligible) part of this energy is collected by a second antenna (pickup) as shown in **Fig. 3-1** .

As the working frequency varies, the stored energy is at its maximum in resonance conditions and it is therefore possible to obtain the resonance peak from the output signal and determine its experimentally determine the frequency. By cutting off the RF power supply the cavity, the output signal decays exponentially according to a time constant. From this value it is possible to derive the merit factor of the resonator.

The maximum attainable value is determined by the power generated by the amplifier, the heat generated by resistive phenomena, the thermal conductivity of the material and the heat dissipation capacity of the helium bath [16].

Fig. 3-1 : Detail of assembled Nb₃Sn/Nb cavity ready for RF characterisation.

3.6 RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

Raman spectroscopy relies upon inelastic scattering of photons. A laser in the visible is used. The laser light interacts with molecular vibrations, phonons or other excitations in the system, resulting in the energy of the laser photons being shifted up or down. The shift in energy gives information about the vibrational modes in the system.

Raman spectroscopy measurements were carried out with a Renishaw λ 633 nm in collaboration with Paola Pavan (Nanostructures and Optics Laboratory NOL group) of the Chemical department (DISC) of UNIPD [17].

3.7 T_C MEASUREMENT

The four-point voltamperometric method is used to measure resistance as a function of temperature. This method makes it possible to eliminate the resistance of the electrical contacts at the ends, which would be much greater than that of the sample and would not give any results. Four contacts are placed on the sample, the outer two inject a sinusoidal current produced by the Keithley 220 current generator, oscillating at a set frequency; the potential drop is measured across the inner contacts with a Keithley 182 nanovoltmeter. By applying Ohm's law the resistance of the sample is obtained.

3.8 A.C. MULTI-HARMONIC MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY CHARACTERIZATION

It's possible to characterize the magnetic behaviour of a material with magnetic susceptibility experiments. AC magnetic susceptibility measures how the sample responds to a sinusoidal variable magnetic field.

1st harmonic real part of the susceptibility measures the type of magnetism of the sample: from weakly positive paramagnetic, when in the normal state it goes to the transition temperature in a state of perfect negative diamagnetism in the superconducting state.

1st harmonic imaginary part of the susceptibility measures the loss currents proportional to the area of the hysteresis loop induced by the excitation variable magnetic field: small Foucault currents induced in the sample in the normal state at the critical temperature there is overlapping more and more high induced from supercurrents.

AC magnetic excitation gives a magnetization where because of inversion symmetry only odd power components are present. In non-linear processes, the anharmonic AC susceptibility can be developing in harmonic Fourier components.

$\chi_{n>1}$ probes only non-linear processes: can separate small phases with different superconductivity critical temperature and flux dynamics. It is connected to non-linear I-V characteristic behaviour. Non-linear I-V characteristics are proportional to the distortion in the magnetization loop from the ellipsoidal curve due to the linear processes **Fig. 3-2**.

A.C. Magnetic Susceptibility measurements were carried out in collaboration with Dr. Daniele Di Gioacchino National Laboratory of Frascati, National Institute of Nuclear Physics (LNF-INFN).

Fig. 3-2 : I-V curve, magnetization for non-linear processes and LNF-INFN measuring equipment[18].

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

This section describes the study and development work undertaken during the thesis.

This work is the natural continuation of the master's thesis focusing on LTD coatings [3]. The optimised process involving the nucleation of the substrate prior to the dipping process was characterised in the various steps in order to evaluate the variations in obtainable morphology, composition and maximum thickness. In addition to the realisation of planar targets, the direct synthesis via LTD of 6 GHz cavities and prototype cavities for axions made it possible to verify the goodness of the process itself in the different geometries.

CHAPTER 4

SET-UP EXPERIMENTAL SYSTEMS

This chapter briefly describes the systems implemented and the processes developed.

4.1 LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION (LTD) SYSTEM

The idea behind this coating process is the introduction of a niobium substrate into a molten bath of Sn and its subsequent annealing.

In particular, the LTD technique can be used for surface coating of large and complex shaped substrates, and there is no need to manipulate hazardous substances such as SnCl_2 to create a nucleation centre.

The LTD system consists of an ultra-high vacuum pumping system, a linear manipulator, a furnace used for heating the crucible containing the tin (lower furnace), a furnace used for annealing of the samples (upper furnace), and a water jacket as shown in **Fig. 4-1**. The main chamber is made of Inconel (Ni-Cr-Fe alloy). The samples are fixed to the manipulator by niobium wires. The system is heated and evacuated to a base pressure of 10^{-8} mbar. The dipping process is divided into various steps as described in **Fig. 4-2** and **Fig. 4-3**. The total protocol of the “hybrid” process with controlled nucleation is summarized below [19].

Fig. 4-1 : Illustrations of the LTD system developed at INFN-LNL with the main components.

Ramping: the lower furnace is switched on to obtain degassing of the crucible in the bottom of the chamber, an hour later the upper furnace is switched on.

Pre-nucleation: the substrates are located at the centre of the chamber in the annealing zone and remain there for 1 to 9 h at 600°C .

Coating: the upper furnace increases the temperature of the system to 1000°C and remains stable from 1 to 9 h.

Dipping: The substrates are immersed in the liquid tin crucible at 1000°C from 0.5 to 7 h by means of the manipulator.

Steam annealing: the samples brought back to the centre of the chamber are heated from 7.5 to 77 h in the presence of the tin vapours of the crucible at 1000°C.

Annealing: the lower furnace decreases in temperature blocking the tin landing on the surface of the samples allowing annealing from 15 to 84 h. The temperature of upper furnace should be near 1000°C.

Cooling: the samples are brought to the upper area of the water jacket to fix the phase.

Fig. 4-2 : Samples position in the chamber in the dipping "hybrid" process with nucleation.

Fig. 4-3 : Temperature profiles of furnaces in the "hybrid" process with nucleation step.

4.1.1 Nb SAMPLE PREPARATION

The material under study is Nb₃Sn synthesised on bulk Nb substrate. In this work are studied: 30 long Nb bulk samples (50x2x1 mm), 16 Nb bulk samples (30x15x3 mm), 3 Nb 6 GHz tesla type cavities, 2 Nb cylinder (similar to cavities for axions), 6 one-inch planar targets 3 mm thick.

The niobium substrates are subjected to ultrasonic bath and subsequent BCP (Buffer Chemical Polishing) HF: HNO₃: H₃PO₄ in a 1:1:2 ratio from five to ten minutes [20]. The substrates prepared for pre-nucleation are subsequently anodized at 20-50-60 V for one minute in NaOH solution to form a 70-150-200 nm of Nb₂O₅ layer. For each run, 2 types of samples at a time have been used: one anodized and one just polished with BCP to evaluate possible change in the film growth.

4.2 Nb₃Sn SPUTTERING SYSTEM

The DC Magnetron Sputtering system consists of an ultra-high vacuum pumping system, a 1-inch magnetron for housing the target obtained via LTD and a heatable sample holder. The system is heated to 750°C and evacuated to a base pressure of 10⁻⁶ mbar. The post process annealing can be performed to increase A15 phase of the deposited film.

Fig. 4-4 : Sputtering system with 1-inch magnetron (left) and detail of sputtering during the deposition process (right).

4.2.1 TARGET AND SAMPLE PREPARATION

The targets include a coupling to the LTD specimen holder and an appropriate sliding path to eliminate the residual tin drop that usually accumulates at the bottom. These parts are removed by mechanical shearing; the one-inch planar target is then cleaned with ethanol before being placed in the system.

Ultrasonically washed quartz is used for deposition.

CHAPTER 5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results obtained in the experimental work will be presented. The characterisation techniques presented above allow the comparison of various types and process conditions, in order to understand which parameters are critical for optimising the growth of the Nb₃Sn film in the various types of substrates used.

5.1 LIQUID TIN DIFFUSION PROCESSES

During the optimization process of the LTD technique, the following parameters were investigated: the influence of Nb anodization, the dipping time and the annealing time in the presence and absence of tin vapours. The morphological and structural characterization allow to understand the quality of the film obtained.

The great constraints found in old processes without Nb anodization are the formation of percolating paths inside the material with consequent incorporation of tin on the surface and small sintering of the grains [3]. By evaluating the liquidus curve in the Nb₃Sn phase diagram under dipping conditions (Sn > 25% due to immersion in molten Sn) Fig. 2-2, it is observed that a fraction of niobium can be solubilized in the bath. As an example, the Nb rod used as a sample holder has a decrease in diameter of 1.5 mm in 24 hours of immersion. The formation of these holes results in an increase in the porosity of the material as well as uncontrolled accumulations of Sn within them. The introduction of the nucleation step mitigates the problem [3], however in the terminal parts of the samples the problem of the macroscopic drop of residual Sn remains due to the effects of the edge of the samples. This problem was solved by engineering the shape of the substrates. The introduction of a preferential drip path at the bottom of the substrates allowed the droplet to be easily eliminated by subsequent mechanical shearing at the end of the process. In the same way that water droplets run down gutter chains, tin droplets follow a small preferential path to accumulate rapidly at the lowest specific point.

5.1.2 NUCLEATION AND COATING

Controlled nucleation occurs if the Nb substrate is anodised, so there is an Nb₂O₅ film on the surface. In VTD processes, SnCl₂ is introduced in order to have a high vapour pressure of Sn at the beginning of the process, whereas in LTD methodology the time is increased and the nucleating agent is not used. The nucleation step in LTD is necessary for the prior formation of Nb₃Sn nuclei before the dipping step. In this way the substrate already has the insoluble A15 phase before immersion, which will decrease the speed of film formation because the growth mechanisms will only occur at the grain boundaries.

Various models attempt to describe the migration and growth of tin within the niobium for the formation of the phase [21]. Empirically, anodization is used to induce nucleation, however many physical models neglect the migration of the oxide within the film as a predominant factor.

In the following, a brief solid-state chemistry model will be presented to understand how oxygen diffuses within the film.

Niobium oxide is known to be an ionic conductor at high temperature due to defect formation; since the oxide is essential for nucleation it should behave as a promoter for compound formation. Nb is known to be a getter and grain boundaries are easily oxidised, in fact Nb naturally has about 6 nm of native oxide [22]. Classically, the compound is obtained from powders. However, the degree of purity is 99.8 % there are always contaminants. Consequently, even in powders there is a small amount of promoter present.

5.1.2.1 MODEL

Considering the oxide under standard conditions (25°C, 1 atm) the Gibbs free energy will be negative (extremely stable compound). The synthesis conditions for the A15 in question are in vacuum ($< 10^{-3}$ mbar) and at high temperature ($T > 500^\circ\text{C}$). The free energy will become positive and the compound metastable. Defects will be formed as already proposed in other papers [5]. Using the Kröger-Vink notation the proposed reactions in this work are:

where e^- denotes the electrons, \circ and $'$ denotes the relative positive and negative charge.

From the notation it can be deduced that the formation of oxygen vacancies causes the presence of electrons which will change the oxidation state. The Nb^{+5} will progressively become $\text{Nb}^{+3} \rightarrow \text{Nb}^{+2} \rightarrow \text{Nb}^0$. At high T, an n-type semiconductor is obtained and no longer an insulating oxide. From eq.(5-1) it can also be assumed that these electrons are used in the Wuppertal process with SnCl_2 to reduce Sn^{+2} to metal on the oxide surface (first part of the equation), this would allow oxidation-reduction. In processes without the nucleating agent, such as the case addressed in this thesis, the electrons are used to reduce Nb (second part of the equation).

Rough assumptions: it is possible to consider the reaction between Sn and the defective oxide **Fig. 5-1 (1)**; in VTD I would also consider the same situation. Formally I dope the oxide with metallic tin which will enter the lattice. The formation of defects increases exponentially with temperature.

The tin could increase hole formation and thus the mobility of species. The notation given here is in agreement with already proposed theory [5] where the following mechanism could also occur:

Given the promoter effect of the oxide, a small polarisation of the Sn-oxide interface can be assumed. To describe the reaction simply, this polarisation is assigned as a small oxidation of a tin monolayer $\text{Sn}_A^{+y}\text{Sn}_B^0\text{O}_j$ as shown in **Fig. 6-1 (2)**. I regard the present tin as a 'reservoir' for the present interphase. it is safe to assume that $B > A$ and $j < B$.

Now the reaction between the defective oxide and niobium, the second interface, can be considered. Similarly to the reasoning above, it is possible to write $\text{Nb}_C^{+z}\text{Nb}_D^0\text{O}_M$ **Fig. 5-1 (3)**. Nb will act as a reservoir at the interface but will not have much influence on nucleation (it will be essential for growth). While the niobium oxide will act as a reservoir of defects caused by the increase in temperature. Considering $C > D$ and $M > j$. We can now consider the interaction of the interfaces just described for the formation of Nb_3Sn at the interface.

Fig. 5-1 : (1) initial situation of interfaces with tin deposition, (2) interface between Sn and oxide layer, (3) defect interface enriched in Nb, (4) interfacial reaction eq.(5-4) and (5) interfacial reaction eq.(5-5).

The Kirkendall effect will be present due to the ambipolar potential that causes the balance of mass and charge:

Semi-reaction at the interface **(4) Fig.(5-1)**: eq.(5-5)

Semi-reaction at the interface **(5) Fig.(5-1)**: eq.(5-6)

From the equations just described we observe the movement of the interface (5) with molar velocity M since $M > j$; therefore through the defects the tin enters the material to increase the crystallite. The movement of the interfaces occurs from right (5) to left (4); therefore, Sn is needed at the grain boundary to continue the reaction. This explains the need for annealing in the presence of steam to stimulate growth and maintain stoichiometry. Considering Nb₃Sn the interface formed first will be on the left and the new one on the right.

The formation of percolative paths in the LTD could also be due to the Kirkendall effect just described. In the VTD, the thermal evaporation process leads to island growth of the Volmer-Weber type; in these processes, too, the Kirkendall effect could be one of the causes of the formation of porosity between the grains.

The migration of oxygen at the interface occurs as a consequence of the increase in defects, the dilution of oxygen at the interface (redistribution of the initial oxide layer) is also plausible. Since $M > j$ because j refers to the quasi-stoichiometric oxide layer, the equation implies an outward transport of niobium. In the past, the possible segregation of Nb within the film in single-step LTD processes [2, 23] was already observed; however, the reasons for this phenomenon were not clear. It is known that annealing by breaking the vacuum is extremely deleterious to the T_c of the film regardless of whether LTD or VTD processes [5, 23]. Since the surface of Nb₃Sn will be equally subject to oxidation one can see the interfaces (4) and (5) of **Fig. (5-1)** inverted. From the same equations exchanged it can be seen that post-process annealing results in the migration of oxygen within the film leading to the increase of impurities at the interface.

Film growth takes place via the grain boundaries, and the mechanisms proposed in the literature [5] fit the model well. The NbO_2 is an n-type semiconductor and is already a metal conductor at 810°C . The coating step takes place at 1000°C and is faster because the charge transfer to the edge will no longer be limited by the ambipolar potential due to the migration of charged species. Similarly, given the high temperature, any oxidised edge of the Nb_3Sn within the film should also exhibit metallic conduction, making it possible to reuse models from the literature.

Eq.(5-5) and eq.(5-6) provide a broad understanding of the formation of the A15 film in question and the possible influence of contaminants. The equations should also remain valid for DCMS depositions, as these could allow us to understand anomalous behaviour of the film (segregations, hole formations [1]) and how layers of Nb or Nb_2O_5 can influence the nucleation-growth of the film.

5.1.2.2 VAPOUR TIN DIFFUSION IN LTD SET-UP

To optimise and understand what happens in the nucleation and coating step of the LTD process, some processes similar to VTD (Siemens process) are carried out as show in **Tab. 1** and **Fig. 5-2**.

SAMPLE	TREATMENT	NUCLEATION STEP $T_{\text{sample}} (^\circ\text{C})$ $t(\text{h})$	COATING STEP $T_{\text{sample}} (^\circ\text{C})$ $t(\text{h})$
N-1	St+BCP+Anod	600 50 min	/
N-2	St+BCP+Anod	600 3	/
N-3	St+BCP+Anod	600 3	1000 3
N-4	St+BCP+Anod	/	1000 3

Tab. 1 : VTD experiments for the study of nucleation and growth steps, for each experiment 4 substrates were inserted one treated only with BCP, the others with further anodization of 20-50-60 V.

Fig. 5-2 : image of the samples anodised at 0-20-50-60 V before the VTD process and after the process; the samples are photographed in the same order.

The lower furnace is maintained at 1000°C , while the substrate is at 600°C . A higher temperature was chosen to operate at a homologous temperature of 0.38 (usually 0.31) to be sure of being in the T-zone of the Thornton diagram to increase the homogeneity of the coating. The higher temperature allows more defects to form and therefore more nucleation sites.

In the N-1 experiment, no crystallites were found; in the EDS, only Nb (N-1-0 samples) and Nb+O (anodised samples) were detected in all samples. Basically, the 50-minute process is insufficient for nucleation under the adopted LTD conditions.

In the N-2 experiment, only the 60 V anodised sample shows the presence of metallic Sn localised on the surface.

Sporadic crystallites of about 250 nm are observed in the N-3 experiment, also concerning growth, which can be traced back to A15 with 17 % Sn in the substrate treated only with BCP. The 20 V anodisation of the N-3-20 sample results in a Sn stoichiometry of A15 of 24.5 % with an average crystallite size of about 250-300 nm observed in **Fig. 5-3**. The nuclei cover 96 % of the survey area and Fourier transform processing of the surface shows the isotropy of the surface elements. The roughness appears to be less than 200 nm. The coating thickness is less than 400 nm as assessed by the Kanaya-OKayama relation. Samples N-3-50 and N-3-60 show crystallites with the same size of 250 nm (variation ± 50 nm) **Fig. 5-4** with stoichiometry Sn 18% and localised areas of metallic Sn as well as O within 400 nm thickness. The surface considered has 95 % coverage with isotropic decoration of the substrate. The roughness appears to be less than 300 nm. In this experiment, traces of Cr contamination < 3 % at the limit of EDS error are present.

Fig. 5-3 : SEM micrograph of the 20 V anodised sample of the N-3 process (left). Stereoscopic reconstruction of the N-3-20 sample in false colours for metrological evaluations (right).

Fig. 5-4 : SEM micrograph of the 60 V anodised sample of the N-3 process (left). Stereoscopic reconstruction of the N-3-60 sample in false colours for metrological evaluations (right).

Experiment N-4 is dedicated to the coating process only (nucleation occurs with the temperature gradient [3]). Crystallites of size larger than 400 nm are observed with a variation of 100 nm in the non-anodised sample (42 % 400 nm size) **Fig. 5-5**. The degree of coverage is 78 % over the surface and the roughness is approximately 400 nm. The stoichiometry is inhomogeneous (Sn 17-30 %) with a possible Sn at the grain boundaries, which is plausible in view of the growth step. In the anodised samples, 350 nm crystallites are observed with variations in the order of 100 nm **Fig. 5-6**. This could be due to Ostwald ripening mechanisms as growth is immediately promoted in this experiment. In the 20 V sample, Sn from 25 % to 28 % is observed in EDS mapping **Fig. 5-6**, while in the 50 V and 60 V samples the variation is more pronounced (Sn 26-37 %). The degree of coverage is 95 % on the surface and the roughness is about 200 nm. There is a 45.01 % anisotropy in the orientation of the crystallites (44°), which can also be seen in the reconstructed image. This phenomenon could always be related to the fact that the larger crystallites tend to grow quickly from the beginning due to the directional flow of tin vapour. The Cr contamination due to the inconel of the chamber increases to 10 % in localised areas and is more pronounced the greater the anodisation.

Fig. 5-5 : SEM micrograph of the non-anodised sample of the N-4 process (left). Stereoscopic reconstruction of the N-4-0 sample in false colours for metrological evaluations (right).

Fig. 5-6 : SEM micrograph of the 20 V anodised sample of the N-4 process, EDS mapping and Fourier analysis (left). Stereoscopic reconstruction of the N-4-20 sample in false colours for metrological evaluations (right).

From the studies conducted so far, it can be deduced that 1 hour of nucleation is insufficient for the formation of crystallites.

If the substrate is not anodised, the degree of surface coating will be lower than for treated substrates because nucleation is not controlled. This is supported by the high surface roughness, since it is practically comparable with the film thickness and the crystallites have a wide distribution (experiments N-3 and N-4). For the anodised samples the nucleation step seems to limit the growth of crystallites in the subsequent coating step. This is because at 600 degrees the mobility is lower and nucleation rather than growth seems to be favoured. From an operational point of view, this is what we are trying to do in order to limit the exposure of the Nb substrate in the subsequent dipping step, thus limiting the formation of percolative paths. The N-4 experiment also provides good results as the degree of coating for the anodised samples does not differ much, so the methodology adopted previously [3] is adequate. In the subsequent experiments for the fabrication of the targets and cavities, the nucleation step is preferred in order to optimise the useful working time and obtain the highest possible degree of initial coating. The stoichiometry of A15 in the cases considered is not very relevant as it is sufficient for the crystallites to be present to avoid dissolution during immersion. Increasing the anodising did not lead to substantial improvements; as the oxide increased, the amount of pollutant coming from the chamber also seemed to increase. However, since increasing the Nb_2O_5 means bringing more contamination into the system, it was decided to keep the anodization at 20 V.

Oxygen Study

The N-3 sample anodised at 20 V was characterised by XPS as it is thin (< 400 nm) and the interfaces presented in the model described above should be more evident (under the synthesis conditions adopted in this thesis work). The XPS analysis in **Fig. 5-7** investigates the chemical composition on the surface of the samples as a function of thickness; they were sputtered through the ion gun for 1 minute to eliminate any native oxide and then the measurements were carried out. The sputtering rate is about 15 nm/min.

In each XPS analysis performed, the first 10 nm of the surface is investigated. From the surveys in **Fig. 5-7** no Cr contamination is observed but C is present as expected as the sample is not characterised in situ. The 3d 5/2 Sn multiplex (black) shows the presence of metallic Sn on the surface (484-485 eV zone) and a more evident peak due to Sn-O bonding. As the tin enters the defects there will be the simultaneous presence of the metallic and oxidised states. Evaluating the relative concentration of Sn-O and Nb-O species in **Fig. 5-8**, it is observed that the oxygen present is more bound to tin. This is consistent with eq. 5-6 because if Nb migrates with oxygen after the coating step the concentration of Nb is low due to mass transport. The multiplex of Nb 3d 5/2 is different from what would be expected in the literature for metallic Nb and Nb_2O_5 in that the dispersion of energies is much wider. This seems to be consistent with other spectra in the literature [24] for Nb_3Sn

where the effect of Nb-Sn binding seems to be to shift the spectrum to higher binding energies (> 1 eV). Evaluating the analyses done at a depth of 90 nm (red spectra), several changes in the shape of the peaks are observed. The relative amount of Sn-O seems to decrease, while Nb-O increases. Since we are about one third of the way through the film and the grains are small, it is safe to assume that the interface between the grain boundaries is very large and globally it is being observed. The 200 nm spectra again show a decrease in Nb-O and an increase in Sn-O; the depth corresponds to about half of the film under study. The interface between the grain boundaries should still be observed but at greater depths (the interfaces will bend due to spherulitic nucleation). In the multiplex of Sn 3d 5/2 the separation between metallic Sn and Sn-O is particularly evident **Fig. 5-7**. Oxygen could migrate according to eq. 5-6 while Sn enters as described in eq. 5-5 as the grain is growing and vacancies repair provides the migration mechanism for Sn. The increase in Sn-O amount could also be explained by the fact that the oxide layer will be completely finished and will no longer have any influence.

Fig. 5-7 : (Left) XPS spectrum of the N-3 sample anodised at 20 V with after sputtering of 1 minute (black), 5 minutes (red) and 7 minutes (blue). (Right) Multiplex detail of previous spectra showing the relevant areas for identifying oxygen bonds.

Fig. 5-8 : Relative concentration obtained from the ratio of areas in the Sn-O/Nb-O bond formation zones as a function of thickness.

The study shows that oxygen acts as a promoter and not as a catalyst, as it remains within the film at the end of the process. The extreme surface of the material is always richer in metallic Sn as it is subjected to the vapour pressure from the crucible. Within the film, both metallic Sn attributable to grain-edge growth and an Nb-Sn-O chemical composition consistent with what is assumed in the model are observed. It can be stated that the present data do not contradict the proposed model, however for the correct validation of the model further experiments and characterisations of the nucleation process and coating only would be needed to observe the differences in BE and correlate them to the surface composition.

5.1.3 DIPPING

The liquid diffusion processes are faster due to the higher diffusion coefficient and the establishment of new mechanisms at the grain boundaries as dissolution and eventual precipitation [3]. In the molten tin, the capillary pressure could greatly emphasise the transport of matter between the edges of the electronic compound. An increase in thickness is observed increasing the dipping time.

To maintain the stoichiometry along the film as the thickness increases, it is also necessary to increase the annealing time. In processes with global annealing times of less than 7 times the dipping time (empirical rule), a higher presence of Sn was found. The graph of the thickness obtainable as a function of immersion time is plotted in **Fig. 5-9**. Using the Fick's law, it is possible to obtain eq. 5-7 for BCP samples and eq. 5-8 for anodized samples with which it is possible to calculate the achievable thickness in a process.

$$x_{BCP}^2 = 156.7 t + 129.5 \quad \text{eq. (5-7)}$$

$$x_{anodized}^2 = 159.6 t + 0.9 \quad \text{eq. (5-8)}$$

Where x is the thickness expressed in μm^2 and t the time expressed in hours.

The slopes are similar, indicating that the basic physical phenomenology is the same. As with VTD processes, the grain edge will drive the formation of the film. The molten material is likely to increase the mobility of chemical species in the system. The error in the plot is due to the variability of the thickness. In BCP samples there is a maximum deviation of $4 \mu\text{m}$, while in anodized samples this decreases on average to $2 \mu\text{m}$. The oxide seems to have a levelling effect during growth allowing an increase in thickness control.

Fig. 5-9 : Plot of the thickness as a function of the dipping time for the BCP non-anodized (blue) and anodized (orange) sample. The data used are those reported in this thesis in the various sections and some taken from the master's thesis [3].

The thickness dependence as a function of dipping time was experimentally verified. The relationships have a limit, since from eq. (5-7) 62 μm should be formed in 24 hours of dipping. Experimentally the observed thickness is 28 μm with a variation of $\pm 5 \mu\text{m}$. Since it is a diffusive process, a plateau may have been reached, in fact the film reaches a thickness like 7 h of dipping in some places and is much thinner in others. Given that the migration of tin occurs at the grain boundary resulting in greater liquefaction of the grain boundary there may be layering for this phenomenon. In other deposition methods, similar phenomena occur but are attributable to material stress. The processes considered here are conducted under thermodynamic conditions and the film modifies the lattice pitch in a way that depends on the amount of Sn, so the two phenomena can coexist and influence each other. Phase A15 does not have a completely homogeneous composition and there may be stress at the grain boundary, which would co-cause the crystallite detachment and hence the decrease in film thickness.

5.1.4 ANNEALING

The heat treatments with Sn steam vapour and without tin flux are essential to control the stoichiometry along the film as already described in previous works [3]. The new experiments (**Tab. 2**) serve to determine whether the optimised process with the nucleation step brings additional benefits compared to the substrate treated only with BCP; in addition, the possible migration of tin and Cr is studied.

SAMPLE	TREATMENT	NUCLEATION STEP	COATING STEP	DIPPING STEP	STEAM ANNEALING	ANNEALING
		T _{sample} (°C)				
		t(h)	t(h)	t(h)	t(h)	t(h)
C1	St+BCP	550	1000	1000	1000	1000
C1A	St+BCP+Anod	3	0.5	0.5	2.5	5
C2	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	970
C2A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	0.5	7.5	15
C3	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	990
C3A	St+BCP+Anod	1	17	0.5	7.5	15
C4	St+BCP	600	800	800	800	800
C4A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	0.5	7.5	15
C5	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	990
C5A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	0.5	7.5	15
C6	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	920
C6A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	0.5	7.5	15
C7	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	930
C7A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	5	5.5	26
C8	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	990
C8A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	24	36	60
Old-1	St+BCP	/	/	1000 3	1000 21	/
Old-2	St+BCP	/	/	1000 3	/	970 19

Tab. 2 : Processes carried out to optimise a thin film for resonant cavities and to study the surface. The cleaning treatment includes ultrasonic degreasing, subsequent BCP and for the samples marked in blue, anodising at 20 V. The steps with the temperatures marked in red were done specifically to evaluate the migration of Cr in a tin-rich surface. Processes C1-C1A and C3-C3A were made to move quickly to the coating step [3].

BCP Samples

The surface of the non-anodized samples subjected to the new process show the formation of percolative paths between the grain boundaries of the Nb₃Sn as shown in the micrograph in **Fig. 5-10 (A)** related to process C1 in **Tab. 2**. The size of the crystallites is about $8 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ in line with what was expected. Twenty-five percent of the surface under analysis shows a layer of metallic tin covering the surface (thickness < 500 nm). The 2D topographic reconstruction in **Fig. 5-10 (B)** shows a surface roughness of $3 \mu\text{m}$ and grain separation is particularly evident with the colour scale. Section analysis in **Fig. 5-10 (C)** shows an inhomogeneous thickness of $14 \mu\text{m}$. The metrological evaluation of the topographic reconstruction in **Fig. 5-10 (D)** for the film section shows a length (along the film) of percolative paths of about $5 \mu\text{m}$ and a width of $6 \mu\text{m}$. The values obtained from the reconstruction reflect the metrological evaluations of the SEM analysis in two dimensions (**A-B**). The shape of the percolative paths is non-linear, probably due to the insoluble barriers presented by phase A15, which deform the path. The film section has a high anisotropy of 81.24 % towards the substrate, where percolative paths are formed by solubilising the Nb. From the data obtained it can be roughly estimated that within the thickness of the film there is a succession of less than 5 crystallites and the one closest to the surface is always larger [3].

Fig. 5-10 : SEM false-colour micrograph according to EDS data of sample C1 (A). (B) Topographical reconstruction of the previous SEM micrograph with two-dimensional display. (C) SEM micrograph of the section of the C1 sample film and relative 3D reconstruction (D) with metrological evaluations. The samples were subjected to metallographic etching with BCP for 20 seconds.

The EDS depth elements profile is obtained evaluating the penetration length of the electron beam as a function of the material observed as shown in **Fig. 5-11 (left)**. Given the high temperature of the annealing step in the absence of steam, which continues for a long time, there is a degassing of the inconel chamber which promotes the formation of a layer rich in Cr. In this type of process, contamination is present between the grain boundaries of the different crystallites, while in the centre of the grain it is not detectable within the EDS limits. The inter-grain concentration of the contaminant decreases with the depth of beam interaction, indicating that the contaminant is superficial and diffuses similarly to Sn via boundaries. This contamination is not present in the surface areas covered by residual Sn, This is also demonstrated in experiments C4 and C6 where the extreme presence of Sn on the surface results in the total absence of the contaminant. The concentration of tin in the area of A15 **Fig. 5-10 (A)** is higher than the stoichiometry of 25 %; analysing the surface of the single grain one immediately observes an enrichment in tin and then a decrease (**Fig. 5-11** orange curve). At the grain boundaries one first observes a low amount of Sn, an effect due to the simultaneous presence of Cr, and then the increase (grey curve). The trends found are consistent with models in the literature for the growth of phase A15 through the edge.

The analysis of the Sn concentration (**Fig. 5-11 right**) relative to the cross-section of the micrograph **Fig.5-10 (C)** determines a global over stoichiometry in Sn in line with that observed in other experiments [3]. The solubilisation of Nb and the formation of preferential pathways probably provides spots for Sn accumulation.

Fig. 5-11 : (Right) EDS depth element profile relative to the micrograph Fig. 5-10(A) ; average indicates the average made in the blue zone, grain indicates the average positioned in the centre of the grain, boundary indicates the analysis made in the intersection of three grains. (Left) Profile of Sn concentration as a function of film thickness relative to the micrograph in Fig. 5-10 (C).

Anodized Samples

The surface of the anodized samples subjected to the new process show the highest level of coverage 98% and the minimization of percolative paths between the grain boundaries as shown in the micrograph in **Fig. 5-12 (A)** related to process C1A in **Tab. 2**. The size of the crystallites is about $7 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ in line with what was expected and it's present only Nb_3Sn . The 2D topographic reconstruction in **Fig. 5-12 (B)** shows an average surface roughness of $1 \mu\text{m}$ and grain separation is not so evident as in the non-anodized sample. The nucleation step resulted in a decrease in roughness. This decrease could be related to the fact that as more crystallites are formed at the same time, they limit growth by steric clutter. The decrease in available space influences the dispersion of grain size by decreasing roughness. The cross-section analysis in **Fig. 5-12 (C)** is for sample C8A, because sample C1A would have too small a cross-section to appreciate the formation of percolative paths within the film. The metrological evaluation of the topographic reconstruction in **Fig. 5-12 (D)** for the film section shows a length (along the film) of percolative paths of about $1.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a width less of $1 \mu\text{m}$. The values obtained from the reconstruction, reflect the metrological evaluations of the SEM analysis in two dimensions of all samples that have received anodising treatment. By increasing the nucleation time, the size of the paths does not seem to decrease significantly. The film section has a high isotropy of 65.27 % towards the substrate, where percolative paths are formed by solubilising the Nb. The increase in the isotropy of the texture is probably related to the fact that the molten tin is not immediately in contact with the Nb substrate. Sn will diffuse within the film preferentially through the liquefaction of the grain boundary in the dipping step. since the grain boundary is spherulitic, the distribution of the viable directions will be less preferential than in the other untreated samples.

Fig. 5-12 : SEM false-colour micrograph according to EDS data of sample C1A (A). (B) Topographical reconstruction of the previous SEM micrograph with two-dimensional display. (C) SEM micrograph of the section of the C8A sample film and relative 3D reconstruction (D) with metrological evaluations. The samples were subjected to metallographic etching with BCP for 10 seconds.

The EDS depth elements profile is shown in **Fig. 5-13 (left)**. In this type of process, contamination is present between the grain boundaries of the different crystallites, while in the centre of the grain it is not detectable within the EDS limits. The inter-grain concentration of the contaminant Cr decreases with the depth of beam interaction, the contaminant is superficial and diffuses similarly to Sn via boundaries. This contamination is not present in the top of the grain richer in Sn with the similar effect of tin veil in non-anodized samples. At the grain boundaries one first observes a correct and constant amount of Sn and a decrease of Cr. The difference to the samples without anodization is the high diffuse presence of Cr within the first 3 μm compared to BCP samples. The highest concentration is however observed within the first μm .

The analysis of the Sn concentration (**Fig. 5-13 right**) relative to the cross-section of the micrograph **Fig.5-12 (C)** determines over stoichiometry in Sn on the surface and a correct stoichiometry in the middle of the film in line with that observed in other experiments [3]. The non-solubilisation of Nb and the low formation of preferential pathways increases the quality of the A15.

Fig. 5-13 : (Right) EDS depth element profile relative to the micrograph Fig. 5-12 (A) ; average indicates the average made in the blue zone, grain indicates the average positioned in the centre of the grain, boundary indicates the analysis made in the intersection of three grains. (Left) Profile of Sn concentration as a function of film thickness relative to the micrograph in Fig. 5-12 (C).

Sample Comparison

From the EDS analysis conducted, it can be stated that the presence of surface Sn results in less contamination by chromium, however, this has a negative influence on the film as NbSn_2 and Nb_6Sn_5 phases are formed.

The XPS analysis in **Fig. 5-14 (left)** investigates the chemical composition on the surface of the samples; they were sputtered through the ion gun for 1 minute and then the measurements were carried out. The BCP-treated sample shows less oxygen than the sample with the initial Nb_2O_5 layer (ΔO 3 %) within the first 10 nm of the material, the investigation depth of these measurements by XPS. The surface composition for the sample with BCP is Sn 28 % comparable with EDS analysis and the presence of Nb_3Sn is confirmed in addition to metallic Sn. The spectrum does not show Cr, the surface tin limits the diffusion of the contaminant.

The spectrum of the anodised sample shows Sn 19 % stoichiometry of phase A15. The concentration is lower than that expected by EDS because a considerable amount of Cr 16% is detected by the peaks in 580 eV region. The niobium oxide as well as promoting the formation of the desired phase could allow an easier migration of the Cr within the film.

A good coating before immersion allows the minimisation of unreacted tin on the surface and avoids the formation of microscopic paths. The absence of metallic tin and the presence of oxide also seem to increase the migration of the Cr contaminant along the grain boundary.

From the diffractometric analysis in **Fig. 5-14 (right)** it is evident how the heat treatments affect the phases obtained. With annealing in the continuous presence of steam (process Old-1 **Tab. 2**), it is not possible to eliminate the residual Sn, which leads to NbSn_2 (green spectrum). The estimated stoichiometry from the spectrum is Sn 24-25 %. The prolonged annealing treatment leads the NbSn_2 phase to lose tin and become Nb_6Sn_5 (Old-2 **Tab. 2**). The estimated stoichiometry from the spectrum is Sn 23-24 %. The sequential heat treatment leads to the stoichiometric A15 phase minimising the others (C1); moreover, the anodization of the substrate reduces the spurious phases even near the surface (C1A). The estimated stoichiometry from spectrums is near Sn 24 % .

Fig. 5-14 : (Right) XPS spectra after the same process for a BCP treated sample (red curve) and an anodized sample (blue curve). (Left) XRD analysis of the samples treated with steam annealing (green), annealing without Sn vapour (black), double sequential annealing in sample without and with anodization (red).

5.1.5 ACCELERATING RESONANT CAVITIES

In order to test the goodness of the new processes in comparison with previously developed LTD techniques [2], three tests were carried out as described in **Tab. 3**. The first only concerned optimisation and morphological analysis, the last test was carried out to synthesise the Nb_3Sn / Nb cavity, which was characterised in RF.

SAMPLE	TREATMENT	NUCLEATION STEP	COATING STEP	DIPPING STEP	STEAM ANNEALING	ANNEALING
		$T_{\text{sample}} (^{\circ}\text{C})$				
		t(h)	t(h)	t(h)	t(h)	t(h)
CT-1A	St+BCP+Anod	600 9	1000 9	1000 0.5	1000 7.5	940 15
CT-2A	St+BCP+Anod	600 9	1000 8.5	1000 0.5	990 7.5	920 45
CT-3A	St+BCP+Anod	600 9	1000 9	1000 0.5	1000 7.5	925 45

Tab. 3 : Processes used to coat 6 GHz cavities in Nb bulk.

Fig. 5-15 : (Blue) cavity of Nb after anodising at 20 V. (Green) Cavity at the end of the CT-1A process with detail of residual tin in the lower iris area. (Orange) Cavity at the end of the CT-2A process with detail of the residual Sn-free internal coating. (Red) Cavity at the end of the CT-3A process.

The cavity is anodised at 20 V for 1 minute **Fig. 5-15 (blue)**. All processes have low annealing temperatures due to instrumental problems. The low annealing time combined with the sub-optimal temperature results in the CT-1A process in the formation of approximately 1 mm of residual tin in the lower iris area (**Fig. 5-15 green**). The CT-2A process has a significantly longer annealing time, resulting in the absence of tin droplets within the surface. As can be seen from the images, in all processes braided wire is added at the end to allow the metal Sn to drop during extraction from the crucible and in the annealing processes. The CT-2A cavity was cut and analysed. The SEM micrograph in **Fig. 5-16 (A)** shows only the presence of A15 crystallites as confirmed by the EDS map and composition. It is not possible to investigate the 3D topography as the substrate is not planar, because it is extracted from the cavity cell. The mechanical cutting of the cell itself resulted in the formation of cracks visible in the image. The EDS elemental composition shows a higher concentration of Sn on the top of the grains while at the edge it progressively decreases **Fig. 5-16 (B)**. Noteworthy is the total absence of Cr within the EDS detectable error. One explanation could be that the inner surface of the material is shielded by the cavity itself. The outer surface has a Cr concentration of 40 % within the first 500 nm. Given the effect, it is thought to implement an Nb screen inside the inconel chamber to achieve the same phenomenon and limit contamination. The diffractogram shows only the presence of Nb₃Sn (inner surface); the average size of the crystallites is 5 µm, comparable to the information obtained from the micrograph. The thickness of the film is about 8 µm in agreement with what is predicted by the equations found.

Fig. 5-16 : (A) SEM micrograph of the cell at the end of the process with relative EDS mapping. (B) EDS compositional analysis as a function of probed thickness.

The CT-3A cavity has been specially designed to be characterised in RF. Although the process is similar to CT-2A, there is a lot of superficial tin on the outside of the cavity, while on the inside dark spots are visible which can be traced back to more Sn-rich areas. The cavity presents quality factors $Q_0 = 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$ as shown in **Fig. 5-17** (comparable with the old process [2]), with a Tc of 11.5 K. It is identified two main causes of this low performances: film poisoning by Cr and problem with the furnace that limited temperature during the annealing step producing a Sn enrichment at the grain boundary.

One problem could be the formation of surface oxide on the top of Nb_3Sn coating. Raman analysis does not show any Nb_3Sn peaks, so no information on this phase can be obtained. However, the absence of peaks for oxide formation is sufficient to exclude oxide formation within the cavity.

Fig. 5-17 : Quality factor as a function of accelerating field and T_c measurement by ejection of trapped flux (left). Raman spectrum of the cell area CT-2A (right).

5.1.6 CAVITIES FOR AXIONS

Two processes were performed on samples simulating the axion cavity as described in **Tab. 4**. The particularity of this type of cavity lies in the 3 cm longitudinal cut which could be filled with metallic Sn.

SAMPLE	TREATMENT	NUCLEATION STEP	COATING STEP	DIPPING STEP	STEAM ANNEALING	ANNEALING
		$T_{\text{sample}} (\text{°C})$ t(h)				
CO-0A	St+BCP+Anod	600	1000	1000	1000	990
		1	17	0.5	7.5	15
CO-1A	St+BCP+Anod	600	1000	1000	1000	990
		9	9	0.5	7.5	15
CO-2A	St+BCP+Anod	600	1000	1000	1000	920
		9	9	0.5	7.5	15

Tab. 4 : Processes for coating samples simulating the axion cavity.

Fig. 5-18 : Photographs of the samples used. The samples are anodised at 20 V. In red the CO-2A sample with detail of the inside of the pill-box.

Fig. 5-18 shows the synthesised samples. An attempt was made to reproduce the same process, but instrumental problems resulted in a decrease in temperature in the second annealing step for sample CO-2A. Due to the geometry of the pill-box, the tests were carried out with different sample holders. In both cases the inner surface of the cavity is optimal, however the second type of CO-2A sample holder also minimises the drops outside the cavity.

In the CO-1A process, conducted at a higher temperature, the stoichiometry is approximately Sn 25 %. From the SEM micrograph in **Fig. 5-19**, the crystalline grains can be seen to be free of surface metallic Sn. Basically, the same characteristics as those described for the anodised samples are present. The CO-2A process, conducted at low temperature, results in the formation of surface metallic Sn with a thickness of less than 500 nm. Topological analyses cannot be conducted due to the geometry of the substrate. The visible cracks are due to mechanical shear of the film. The thickness obtained is about 9 μm for both types of samples.

Fig. 5-19 : SEM micrographs of the inner surface of sample CO-1A and CO-2A.

Sample CO-0A has dimensions 35x11x1 mm and the residual post-process drop was removed by mechanical shearing as described above. This sample was synthesised with the aim of being characterised by A.C. multi-harmonic magnetic

susceptibility and is placed in this section, as it is the most relevant characterisation in order to obtain the critical magnetic field. In the future, a sample similar to the axion cavity will be synthesized with the parameters used for CO-0A. The characteristics in terms of morphology and structure are similar to those discussed above, i.e. presence of phase A15 with stoichiometry of about 25 %.

From the analysis of the imaginary component in the third harmonic characterisation, one is able to investigate the superconducting phases within the film. The susceptibility depends on the oscillation of the ratio between the applied and penetrated magnetic field. Basically, the presence of different superconducting phases within the film is noted. They always belong to the A15 phase of Nb_3Sn but have different stoichiometry. The stoichiometry is obtained from T_c [4]. The analysis in Fig. 5-20 shows that as the applied magnetic field increases, the intensity of the peaks decreases; this indicates that the phases with a lower critical field (lower stoichiometry) return to normal conductivity. The predominant A15 phases within the film have T_c 12.8 K (Sn 23.5 %) and T_c 14 K (Sn 24 %). The data obtained are in line with the other characterisations carried out. At 6 T only the Nb_3Sn with Sn 24 % is present and gives an indication of the critical magnetic field that can reach the material in service. The graph in Fig. 5-20 (right) provides information on the magnetic field pinning. From the plot it can be deduced that the pinning takes place inside the material and not on the surface, basically Nb_3Sn behaves as a bulk and not as a thin film. The pinning is however low, a sign of pure A15 phases. From a practical point of view an axion cavity can be made by this process. Currently the maximum value at which cavities have been tested is 6 T in line with the data obtained. The magnetic field in these types of cavities must penetrate, and the fact of having bulk and not surface pinning could be of considerable importance. More tests and characterisations need to be conducted for a better understanding of the phenomenology.

Fig. 5-20 : A.C. multi-harmonic magnetic susceptibility characterisation and pinning analysis.

5.1.7 Nb₃Sn PLANAR TARGET

The synthesised targets will be used for DCMS depositions. The processes used are listed in **Tab. 5** and show in **Fig. 5-21**.

SAMPLE	TREATMENT	NUCLEATION STEP	COATING STEP	DIPPING STEP	STEAM ANNEALING	ANNEALING
		T _{sample} (°C)				
		t(h)	t(h)	t(h)	t(h)	t(h)
T1	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	930
T1A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	5	5.5	26
T2	St+BCP	600	1000	1000	1000	990
T2A	St+BCP+Anod	9	9	24	36	60

Tab. 5 : processes used for the synthesis of 1-inch planar targets.

Fig. 5-21 : Images of the sample after anodising (blue), of the T1A process (green) and T2A process (red). Last image referring to the optimised geometry of the samples to be used in the future (grey).

The first process T1 and T1A was conducted at sub-optimal temperatures resulting in residual surface tin. The second process T2 and T2A have a lower amount of surface tin, however of the Nb₆Sn₅ phase is present.

In **Fig. 5-22 (A)** relative to the EDS mapping of the anodized sample (T2A), show a surface contamination of Cr greater than 40 % within the first micron. At the diffractometer, no Cr-containing phases are present long the bulk of the film. The average stoichiometry of the film is 26 % and the average thickness is 27 μm in accordance with the predictions within the error.

The presence of the spurious phase could be due to an annealing time that is too short compared to the immersion period. Given the large surface area, it is possible to assess the composition as a function of the thickness probed with x-rays. **Fig. 5-22 (B)** shows the spectra acquired at different angles of incidence to probe for stratification. It is observed that as the beam penetration increases, the Nb₆Sn₅ phase decreases. In detail, high resolution analyses were carried out to obtain the stoichiometry of the A15 phase. The data shown in image **(C)** are obtained from the Rietveld refinements. The density of phase A15 gradually rises to 4 μm and then falls. The density trend for the Nb₆Sn₅ phase is different and falls progressively. The trend of the spurious phase is consistent with what is expected since the surface is

increasingly rich in tin, while inside the material diffusion at the grain boundaries will form the correct phase. The change in the density of A15 can be explained by observing the change in stoichiometry **(D)**. In the first layers a stoichiometry of 22 % is observed, then at about 6 μm a second peak appears. The analysis shows A15 phases with different stoichiometry from 22% to 24%. The compositional inhomogeneity of the A15 phase leads to a decrease in the density obtained.

Fig. 5-22 : (A) SEM micrograph with EDS mapping of the T2A target section and its thickness-dependent Sn concentration profile. (B) Spectra acquired at different beam angles to probe possible stratifications; the upper graph shows in detail the peaks (100) of phase A15 as a function of lattice pitch for stoichiometry evaluation. (C) Density profile of phases A15 and Nb₃Sn as a function of x-ray penetration into the material. (D) Stoichiometric variation of Nb₃Sn as a function of x-ray penetration, extrapolated Tc is shown [4].

Overall, a stratification of Nb₃Sn is observed, and the stoichiometries obtained agree with the AC susceptibility characterisations set out above. The graph **(D)** shows the Tc associated with the stoichiometries. The highest critical temperature of 14 K with stoichiometry of about 24% is observed.

From the last analysis it would appear that the SC film at adequate stoichiometry starts at 1/3 of the available film. The surface is always richer in Sn, which could cause problems in the Nb₃Sn/Nb accelerating cavities. Cortical currents enter the coating for more than 500 nm and encountering the suboptimal film could increase dissipation and consequently explain the low performance.

5.2 Nb₃Sn DC MAGNETRON SPUTTERING

The **Tab. 6** shows the sputtering process parameters and the target used for Nb₃Sn on quartz deposition. Only anodized targets synthesized with the optimized process is used **Fig. 5-23**.

SAMPLE	WORKING PRESSURE (Ar)	DEPOSITION	DEPOSITION	Annealing
		Current (A) t(min)	Tsample (°C)	Tsample (°C) t(min)
S0	5*10 ⁻³ mbar	0.1 A 50 min	750	/
S1	1*10 ⁻² mbar	0.1 A 26 min	750	/
	6*10 ⁻³ mbar	0.1 A 120 min		
S2	5*10 ⁻³ mbar	0.1 A 30 min	750	750°C 15 min

Tab. 6 : Deposition processes, S0 carried out with 1-inch Nb targets, S1-S2 carried out with anodized targets synthesised via LTD.

Fig. 5-23 : Nb₃Sn target via LTD used and Nb₃Sn/quartz samples obtained.

The aim is the deposition of at least 1 μm of Nb₃Sn on quartz with a Nb₃Sn thick film made via LTD. The post-process annealing in process S2 is used to enhance the correct phase. The S0 process performed with a target of Nb resulted in a sputtering yield of 5 nm/min. Based on the data obtained, the S1 process was carried out. This process had the complication of arc formation, so the pressure was raised to clean the target. As a result, more of the available film was eroded with the 27 μm target and the correct stoichiometry could not be obtained. The S3 process was started at high pressure and immediately decreased, thus avoiding arcs. The process was stopped when the voltage dropped from 380 V to less than 350 V. The decrease was interpreted as the end of the film available for deposition. Post-process annealing has the task of increasing the A15 phase and decreasing stress. Of the 27 μm available, a difference of 21 μm is obtained at the profilometer. In the rail track, Nb 100 % is observed as a clear sign of preferential sputtering. Due to the presence of bulk Nb all the available film has been eroded.

The micrograph in **Fig. 5-24 (A)** relative to the S2 process shows the morphology of the deposited film. The film has a thickness of 1.2 μm with a deposition rate of 40

nm/min, the thickness is validated by both SEM and profilometer. The stoichiometry at EDS analysis is about 25%, the mapping shows clusters at different concentrations (Sn 20%). The topological analysis in **Fig. 5-24 (B)** shows a roughness of less than 1 μm like the VTD processes described above. The crystalline grain size varies from 250 nm to 400 nm for larger clusters. The texture shows an isotropy of 54.33 %; being a directional PVD process the figure is in line with expectations and comparable with VTD processes.

The XRD analysis of the sputtered film in **Fig. 5-24 (C)** shows the A15 phase and the spurious phase as the initial target film. The extrapolated stoichiometry from the target is Sn 24% (Tc 14 K) and 23 % (Tc 12 K) from the film [4]. The presence of chromium in the deposited film is not detected with EDS instrumentation, the absence of phases containing Cr is also confirmed by the diffractometric analysis.

The determination of the critical temperature as a function of the resistance **(D)** of the film is the opposite of what was expected. At Tc a superconductor exhibits zero electrical resistance; the deposited film shows an increase in resistance as the temperature decreases. This anomalous behaviour may be due to fracturing of the film as a result of the deposition parameters, or to uncontrolled martensitic transition. Another explanation could be attributable to oxidised grain boundaries as the basic vacuum of the system may not have been adequate. The semiconductive behaviour is in agreement with the model presented above. The lattice variation of the film **(C)** could be a convolution between O and Sn present in the coating.

Fig. 5-24 : (A) SEM micrograph of the deposited Nb₃Sn sample and EDS mapping of the entire micrograph. (B) Topographic reconstruction of the film with metrological analysis such as roughness and texture of the deposition. (C) Diffractogram of the target synthesised via LTD (goniometric scan) and of the deposited film (GIXRD). (D) Tc characterization of the sputtered film.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

6.1 CONCLUSIONS

- In this thesis work, the steps for the synthesis of Nb₃Sn via Liquid Tin Diffusion were studied in detail. After determining the key parameters in the process control, thin films were synthesised for application in resonant cavities. The experimental determination of the relationship between thickness and dipping time allowed the synthesis of 1-inch planar targets. It has been demonstrated that an Nb₃Sn film can be deposited directly from an Nb₃Sn/Nb target synthesised via LTD.
- It has been demonstrated that the controlled nucleation process is fundamental for an efficient success of the process in terms of film quality. The macroscopic tin droplets are considerably reduced, and spurious phases are minimized in the A15 allowing a better maintenance of the ideal stoichiometry of 25 % of Sn.
- The study of the effect of the oxide made it possible to choose the initial thickness of Nb₂O₅, and the hypothesis that the A15 phase is formed before the dipping step was tested. Nucleation enabled the minimisation of percolation paths.
- The dipping time is the predominant factor in increasing the film thickness. The relationships found for Fick's law allow to estimate the thickness as a function of the immersion time. The 5-hours processes allow to obtain 27 μm sufficient for the deposition of 1 μm of Nb₃Sn via DC magnetron sputtering.
- The "hybrid" heat treatment is essential to obtain a correct stoichiometry and minimization of the spurious phases. The new experiments serve to determine whether the optimised process with the nucleation step brings additional benefits compared to the substrate treated only with BCP; in addition, the migration of tin and Cr is studied. Contamination was always present in all samples even in the past due to the inconel chamber. Cr migration is favoured at the grain edge and the concentration is higher if the substrate is anodised. In areas of residual Sn the contamination is absent. Nucleation enabled the minimisation of percolative paths from 5 μm length (BCP) to 1.5 μm (anodized).
- The new process is adaptable to covering resonant cavities. The film is optimal from a morphological point of view, but the performance is comparable with that obtained in the past for accelerating cavities. To further improve performance, it is necessary to eliminate sources of contamination.
- The films have a maximum critical magnetic field of 6 T, which is comparable with fields already used for axion cavities; however, higher fields are required. Analysis of vortex pinning shows that the film is like bulk Nb₃Sn; in addition, the A15 phase is pure (little pinning effect). Cr contamination does not interact much with the Nb₃Sn phase. The geometry is irrelevant, in fact the structural morphological characteristics are comparable with planar samples. The actual cavity will be covered soon.
- The single-use thick film planar targets of Nb₃Sn via LTD technique for DC magnetron sputtering depositions were obtained and successfully used. Analysis of the density profile of the phases present determined that at about 1/3 of the

available film coexist 24% A15 and 23.5% Sn phases in agreement with the magnetic susceptibility measurements, while the surface is richer in Sn.

- The characterization of the sputtered film on quartz from Nb_3Sn target via LTD confirms the A15 phase in the deposit. The coating has characteristics and stoichiometry comparable to the starting target thick film of Sn 24 %. Given the low superconducting performance achieved, it is necessary to optimise the deposition process.
- To eliminate chromium contamination in the LTD process, a niobium screen will be inserted inside the chamber and the deposition system will be modified with a shutter to perform a pre-sputtering with which to clean the target from unreacted Sn or Cr.

6.2 FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The study will continue with the following programme:

- The system dedicated exclusively to the sputtering of Nb_3Sn will be completed shortly **Fig. 6-1** . Optimal parameters will be sought with the 4-inch magnetron and then an attempt will be made to reproduce the results with LTD targets. Sputtering will be carried out first on dielectric substrates and then on Cu. At this stage it will be possible to deposit half-cells for axion cavities.
- At the same time, the cylindrical targets will be coated with LTD.

Fig. 6-1 : Dedicated system for Nb_3Sn deposition via DCMS and detail of the 1-inch magnetron inside the vacuum chamber.

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